

SHORT NOTES

REDUCTION OF VANADIUM SALTS BY NASCENT HYDROGEN FROM HYDROCHLORIC ACID AND METALS: MAGNESIUM, ZINC AND CADMIUM

By B. S. SRIKANTAN

Mellor ("Comprehensive Treatise on Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. I, p. 334, Longmans, 1920) summarises the theories on nascent hydrogen by saying "that the so-called nascent hydrogen is assumed to consist of electrically neutral atoms (mono) of hydrogen and the difference in the nascent hydrogen derived from different sources is due to the effective concentration of mono-atomic hydrogen which in turn is determined by the rate of conversion of the mono-atomic into ordinary hydrogen." In a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1951, 28, 69) it was shown that the rate of reduction of KMnO_4 by nascent hydrogen from $\text{Zn-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ was twice as fast as that from $\text{Cd-H}_2\text{SO}_4$, and the rate of production of nascent hydrogen from $\text{Zn-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ was concluded to be twice that from $\text{Cd-H}_2\text{SO}_4$. Tommasi (*Ber.*, 1898, 31, 345, 1878; *Chem. News*, 1879, 40, 245; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1897, 1, 555) pointed out the inability to explain why Zn-HCl reduced salts of vanadium pentoxide to dioxide stage, while Mg-HCl reduced only to trioxide stage under similar conditions. Magnesium precedes zinc in E.M.F. series, but the order of activity in the reduction of V_2O_5 in HCl is reverse. In this note the observations of Tommasi on the reduction of V_2O_5 have been repeated with Mg , Zn and Cd , and an explanation for the order of nascent activity of hydrogen from these metals and acid in the reduction of V_2O_5 is put forward.

Pure vanadium pentoxide was dissolved in hot HCl (conc.) to a clear solution, and diluted. Pure metals, viz., Zn , Cd and Mg , almost with equal surfaces, were put into the solution and kept shaken. After complete reduction in each case, the colour of the solution was noted. Of these, zinc reduced the yellow solution to a lavender colour; Mg , though evolved hydrogen rapidly and went into solution, could reduce it only to the green V_2O_3 stage. The results are tabulated below.

TABLE I.

Stages of oxides of vanadium.	Corresponding chlorides.	Colour of salt solution.	Metals giving reduction to stage.
V_2O_5	VOCl_3	Yellow	...
VO_2	VOCl_2	Blue	Cd
V_2O_3	VOCl	Green	Mg
V_2O_2	VCl_2	Lavender	Zn

The order of decreasing activity of nascent hydrogen is from Zn-Mg to Cd .

The production of neutral hydrogen atoms from hydrogen ions involves the ionisation of the metal by transfer of electric charges.

Therefore the production of nascent hydrogen and its activity are the function of the ionisation potential of the particular metal. The following table records the second ionisation potential (e) and the ionic radii (r) of Mg, Zn and Cd from Pauli.

TABLE II

Metal.	e .	r .	e/r .
Zn	17.89 volts	0.74 $\text{\AA}$	24.2
Mg	14.96	0.65	23.0
Cd	16.84	0.97	17.3

It is seen from the above table that the value of e/r for these metals are in the order of Zn-Mg and Cd, which is also the order of reduction of V_2O_5 in HCl by these metals. Therefore it can be concluded that the nascent activity of hydrogen from different sources is a function of ionisation potential and the ionic radii of the metals generating the hydrogen. e/r has the dimensions of force and may be termed "field intensity".

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USE OF THIAZOLIDONES AND 5-AMINOTHIAZOLIDONES AS ANALYTICAL REAGENTS FOR COPPER AND SILVER

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In course of our investigations on "thiazolidone compounds", it was considered of interest to study all their possible applications in analytical procedures, viz., for the estimation of silver (Das and Rout, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1955, **14B**, 16). Another compound of the same series has been examined here for its use in the estimation of copper. One of another type of thiazolidone derivatives, viz., 5-amino-2-*p*-nitrophenylimino-4-thiazolidone, has also been studied for the estimation of silver.

Estimation of Copper.—The reagent, 2-*p* tolylimino-4-thiazolidone, was prepared by refluxing *p*-tolylthiourea and monochloroacetic acid in absolute alcohol using anhydrous sodium acetate as the condensing agent. Stock solutions of copper sulphate were prepared and were estimated by the iodimetric method. The reagent being insoluble in water, a solution of the reagent in minimum volume of alcohol was employed.

To a known volume of the standard $CuSO_4$ solution, maintained at pH 5.2 by adding 100 c.c. NaAc-HAc buffer, an excess of the warm alcoholic solution of the reagent (2%) was added dropwise with constant stirring till complete precipitation. The complex formed was slightly warmed for about 5 minutes on a water-bath and allowed to stay overnight. Some of the reagent came down along with the complex that had precipitated. This could not, however, be removed by any of the solvents or solvent mixtures without affecting the weight of the complex. Hence, the precipitate was